

Full Lagrangian Theory from Constant Speed Lorentz Invariant $-Et+px$?

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A free particle's motion may be described by the simple equation $x=vt$. One may ask: What more does one need to present than that? We suggest that due to special relativity, $x=vt$ is not sufficient, especially in cases for which one has $v(x)=\text{constant}$ to first order, but with acceleration occurring at the same time. Furthermore, even in the free particle case, $x=vt$ is not sufficient quantum mechanically.

The reason for this is that a key piece of physics is missing from $x=vt$, namely Newton's notion of rest mass as inertia. Inertia means that some force is required to move a rest mass to the speed v . One may argue that once it is moving with a constant v and not interacting, then $x=vt$ is the full description. According to special relativity, however, this is not the case due to the Lorentz invariant $-E^2 + c^2 p \cdot p = -m_0^2 c^4$ ((1)), which is used to derive the formulas for E and p (energy and momentum in the first place). ((1)) holds even if the particle is not interacting. There is also another Lorentz invariant $-Et+px = A(t,v)$, and we suggest that this also carries essential physical information as it is independent of $x=vt \rightarrow x=E/p t$ (particle with rest mass). Given $-Et+px=A(t)$ for a free particle, it is understood that $x=vt$. Nevertheless, $-Et+px=A(t)$ contains independent information and we suggest trying to extract $x=vt$ information from $-Et+px=A(t)$. This may seem unnecessary given that one knows $x=vt$, a priori. Any expression one obtains from $-Et+px = A(t)$ cannot contradict $x=vt$ with v constant and so is essentially a statement of $v=\text{constant}$. In particular, we will show/argue that the expression obtained from $-Et+px=A(t)$ is $d/dt dL/dv=0$ where $L = -E+pv = -\text{sqrt}(1-vv/cc)$, i.e. t factored out of $A(t,v)$ and then only v used as a variable. $d/dt dL/dv=0$ reduces to $dv/dt=0$ or $v=\text{constant}$ and so one may ask: What possible relevance can $d/dt dL/dv =0$ have?

We argue that its relevance emerges when one considers motion due to a conservative force $F = -\text{grad } V(x)$. In such a case, each dx region is considered to have a constant $v(x)$ and so the idea of a constant speed must still be relevant, but one must still respect special relativity. The simplest thing to do would be to write $dv(x)/dt = \text{function}(x)$ linked to $F(x)$, because when $F=0$, $dv/dt=\text{constant}$. This is in fact what one does for a constant rest mass in Newtonian (nonrelativistic physics). To be more general, however, one must include special relativistic information, even for a constant speed, and that full information is contained in $d/dt dL/dv$ partial. Instead of setting this equal to 0, one must set it equal to an appropriate function of x , but one sees that there is a difference between a formalism using $dv/dt = \text{Function of } x$ linked to force and $d/dt dL/dv$ partial = Different function of x linked to force. The latter respects special relativity and L is the same function of v obtained from the special relativistic treatment of a free particle. This is why $L = -m_0 \text{sqrt}(1-vv/cc) - V(x)$ in special relativity.

In short, we argue that full Lagrangian theory emerges from special relativistic considerations of a free particle which contain more information than $x=vt$.

Free Particle Motion and Why $x=vt$ is Not Sufficient

A free particle moves as:

$$x=vt \text{ ((2))}$$

As long as it is not interacting, one might argue that ((2)) represents the complete physics one needs to know. Even though a force was needed to accelerate a rest mass, m_0 , and there is an $E=m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p=m_0v/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ (one dimension for simplicity), these are interaction related pieces of information. We argue that such thinking is not correct even if an interaction does not occur because relativity links x,t to E,p even for no interaction through $-Et+px = A(t,v)$. One may argue that this is simply the equation of a Lorentz invariant and has no physical consequences, i.e. that $x=vt$ is the full physics of a noninteracting free particle. We have argued in previous notes, however, that $-Et+px = A(t)$ gives rise to free particle quantum mechanics because x,t and $x+hbar/p, t+hbar/E$ both give rise to the same $A(t)$ suggesting interactions could occur at different places for the same $A(t)$ value. This, however, is again linked to interactions. A probabilistic theory, with complex probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, shows how E,p,x and t are linked. $x=vt$ is no longer the full description as a particle may hit with p a different x points, e.g. x and $x+hbar/p$. Thus, it is the special relativistic invariant $-Et+ipx=A(t)$ which carries more information and this extra information should be respected even in the non-quantum situation. One might argue that $\exp(-Et+ipx)$ is only relevant when an interaction occurs, but that is not true as $\exp(ipx)$ may acquire a phase in space and $\exp(-iEt)$, one in time. These manifest themselves at an interaction, but one must be aware of them, even when the particle is not interacting. Certainly, $x=vt$ does not provide this information.

The Notion of Inertia

Even though $x=vt$ describes center-of-mass motion of a free particle, this is not the full physics present. A particle moving with v and having rest mass m_0 underwent an acceleration, i.e. an interaction with a force. If one has two rest masses, m_1 and m_2 , at rest, then they represent a force called inertia, introduced by Newton. A force is needed to make m_1 and m_2 move, but this implies specific v_1, v_2 (speeds) regardless of how small. It seems then, that to describe inertia, one requires a function:

$$p(m_0, v), \text{ where } m_0 \text{ is the rest mass and } v \text{ a speed, regardless of how small ((3))}$$

$p(m_0, v)$ is a measure of the hit needed to make m_0 start to move, or the hit required to suddenly stop an object with m_0, v from moving. For example, it might hit a "brick wall". In such a case, m_1, v_1 and m_2, v_2 could create the same p math value and so should have the same physical implications for a sudden hit. This seems to be the case experimentally as $dp = \text{Integral } F dt = \text{impulse}$. Thus, it is a combination of m_0 and v which seems to be the relevant physical quantity for a sudden hit interaction. The question then becomes: How does one determine $p(m_0, v)$?

We consider the special relativistic scenario of a rest mass m_0 at rest at $x=0, t$. In a frame moving at $-v$, this is seen to move with v . Such a particle will be seen to move at $x=vt$. This means that $x=0, t$ in the rest frame becomes x', t' such that $x'=vt'$ as seen in the moving frame. In other words, there is an x,t transformation. Physically, however, a force impacted m_0 and to only consider x', t' and $x'=vt'$ means completely ignoring the force required to move m_0 and the impulse hit that a moving m_0 can create. Even though no interaction is occurring, a free particle

still should have a state property of $p(m_0, v)$. In fact, given that $x=0$, t maps to x', t' , m_0 should map to a vector p and a number E . This begs the question: What is the physics behind E ? To describe it simply, we start with first trying to identify E, p . We consider a transformation of the type:

$$\begin{bmatrix} g(v) & vg(v) \\ vg(v) & g(v) \end{bmatrix} \quad ((4))$$

Then, $(0, m_0 c)$ transforms to:

$$p = g(v) v m_0 c \quad \text{and} \quad E = g(v) m_0 c^2 \quad ((5))$$

One expects $E > m_0 c^2$ as the inertia is now greater due to the motion. This is a physical statement. Furthermore, there should be an equivalence between m_0 and E, p because they describe the same physical state seen from two different frames, a rest one and a moving one. Given a matrix ((4)), an invariant in linear algebra is given by the square of the vector components. We thus suggest putting these ideas together to write:

$$-E^2 + c^2 p^2 = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((6))$$

From this one, finds that $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ ((7))

A second Lorentz invariant which exists is:

$$-Et + px = A(t) \quad \text{with } x=vt \text{ being understood as the center-of-mass motion} \quad ((8))$$

$x=vt$ or $x = p c^2 / E t$ for a particle with rest mass is independent of ((8)), and we argue that ((8)) contains relevant special relativistic information not contained in $x=vt$. We go further and argue that one may extract $x=vt$ from ((8)) using a math formalism which we describe in the next section.

We originally discussed the sudden impact linked with $p(m_0, v)$ as being physical. What then is the physical information contained in E . We show later that one may obtain a relativistic scheme which becomes $m_0 dv/dt = \text{Force}$ in the $v \ll c$ limit. In such a case, one may obtain $E = m_0 c^2 + .5 m_0 v^2$. This energy does not need to be linked to a sudden hit. For $p = m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2$, the sudden hit is the same, but $.5 m_1 v_1^2 \neq .5 m_2 v_2^2$, showing that there is more than a sudden hit interaction in nature and that both p and E are physically relevant.

Lagrangian Mechanics

A free particle center-of-mass is described by $x=vt$, but we argue that $-Et + px = A(t)$ should contain more information than this, and yet at the same time be able to demonstrate that $x=vt$ holds. That, we argue, is the basic idea of trying to develop a Lagrangian mechanics for a free particle. At first this seems absurd, as $v = \text{constant}$, or $x=vt$ describes the full motion. Any

equation resulting from a new formalism is simply going to yield $v=\text{constant}$ or $dv/dt = 0 \rightarrow x=vt$. There is no more dynamical information than this as no interaction occurs.

The key point we wish to make is that if there is a force in the problem, then the traditional Newtonian viewpoint is that one may break x into equally spaced dx units (or if working with t , dt equally spaced dt units) and that one has $v(x)=\text{constant}$ in each dx . There is, however, a force which accelerates the particle in dx and so the full physics should be a combination of constant v theory with one which handles interactions and this is not $x=vt$, but rather $-Et+px=A(t)$, we argue.

As a first step, consider only considering a $v(x)$ in dx . Then one may note that $v(x)$ changes in x and also in time. One may write dv/dt and equate it to some function of force(x). This is in fact Newtonian mechanics for constant rest m_0 , but completely ignores special relativistic physics included in $-Et+px=A(t)$. We suggest that so-called constant $v(x)$, but with acceleration occurring, may be handled using an expression from $-Et+px=A(t)$ which demonstrates $v=\text{constant}$ for force=0, but is then combined with a function of force for the case of acceleration. One may show that using this approach one does in fact obtain a more general result than by considering dv/dt , but that this result yields $m_0 dv/dt$ when $v \ll c$.

We start with

$$-Et+px = A(t,v) \quad ((9)) \text{ with } x=vt \text{ understood to be implicitly contained in } ((9))$$

The goal is to extract $x=vt$. We first consider a certain frame with

$$x_0=0, t_0=0 \text{ and a } x_f, t_f \quad ((10))$$

$$((9)) \text{ may be written as: } \int_{t_0}^{t_f} (-E+pv) dt = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} (-E+pv) dt$$

$$= \int_{t_0}^{t_f} -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((11))$$

$((11))$ holds for a particle constant v value, but one may consider a different frame in which one has $v+dv$. In such a case, $x_0=0, t_0=0$ holds, but $t_f, x_f \rightarrow t_{f1}, x_{f1}$ and $A(t_f, v) = A(t_{f1}, v+dv)$. If on the other hand, one keeps t_f constant in the integral in $((11))$, then replacing v with $v+dv$ in $((11))$ does not correspond to a $-v-dv$ frame and one must insist on the change part of the integral $((11))$ being 0 because $A(t_f, v)$ must hold. Furthermore, one may change t_f to be any value and so one wants the change to be 0 at each dt point.

$$D \int_{t_0}^{t_f} -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc} dt = 0 = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} -m_0 \frac{d}{dv} \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \delta x/dt \quad ((12))$$

One may interchange d/dt and δ and perform an integration by parts and so the function in question which should be 0 is

$$m_0 \frac{d}{dt} \sqrt{1-vv/cc} = 0 \quad ((13))$$

For a free particle, ((13)) indicates nothing more than $dv/dt=0$ or $x=vt$, but if a particle moves at constant v in dx , but at the same time is interacting due to a force $(V(x))$, then the RHS of ((13)) would no longer be 0. It would be a function linked to Force(x).

Now one may try to argue that one does not need ((13)) and can simply use $dv/dt = \text{function of Force}(x)$ to describe the problem. In fact, this is Newtonian mechanics for constant rest mass. In particular, Newton argued that:

$$\text{Force}(x) = dp/dt = m_0 dv/dt \quad ((14))$$

Is ((14)) the same as ((13))? The answer is no, but ((13)) reduces to ((14)) for $v \ll c$ if one replaces the RHs of ((13)) with $F(x)$, i.e.

$$d/dt \{ m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \} = \text{Force}(x) \quad ((15))$$

$$\text{For } v \ll c \quad m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv/cc} \rightarrow m_0 v \quad ((16))$$

As a result, we suggest that free particle special relativity described by $-Et+px = A(t,v)$ as a Lorentz invariant allows one to extract $x=vt$ in the $v=\text{constant}$ case from the more general $-Et+px=A(t,v)$. This more general case then applies to the case of an interaction as E,p are interaction variables even if one considers a constant $v(x)$ motion to first order.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $x=vt$ is not sufficient to describe the physics associated with a free particle, although the center-of-mass does move as $x=vt$. We have argued before that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px = A(t,v)$ is more general as it incorporates ideas of special relativity (frame invariance), while at the same time including $x=vt$. If one has a free particle and only wishes to consider classical physics, one might argue that $x=vt$ suffices. (For free particle quantum mechanics it does not and we have argued in previous notes that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a complex probability which follows from the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$). Quantum mechanics aside, if one has a Force of x ($F = -\text{grad } V(x)$ for a conservative force), then one may break x into tiny equal dx units or time into tiny equal dt units. $v(x)$ or $v(t)$ is constant to first order in such a unit, but there is actually an interaction occurring and we argue that the information in $-Et+px = A(t,v)$ is relevant. In particular, writing $dv/dt = \text{function of force}$ is not enough as we show. As a result, we argue that even though it seems absurd to try to extract $x=vt$ from $-Et+px$, by obtaining a more complicated expression which ultimately is equivalent to $dv/dt=0$ in the $v=\text{constant}$ case, the expression is relevant to the case in which one has a force(x). As a result, we write: $-Et+px = t(-E+px) = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv/cc} = \int_{(t_0,t_f)} -m_0 dt \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. We suggest that if $v \rightarrow v+dv$, one has the result for a different frame, but in frame 1, one must have $A(t_f,v)$ and so any extra piece due to dv should be 0. Using integration by parts, one has: $d/dt m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc} = 0$. Again, this is no different for $v=\text{constant}$, but if there is a force present, we do not use $dv/dt = \text{function force}(x)$, but rather $m_0 d/dt \sqrt{1-vv/cc} = \text{function force}(x)$. For $v \ll c$,

the latter becomes the former, but otherwise it includes relativistic effects. We thus suggest that the full Lagrangian formalism